

The Ediz method for subtraction with borrowing

Süleyman Ediz¹

Abstract

In this study, we propose a new and simplified viewpoint for subtraction with borrowing

Introduction

Traditional Subtraction with Borrowing, which involves borrowing tens from neighbouring digits when a larger digit is needed to subtract from a smaller one, can be challenging for many people.

In this study, we propose a new and simplified viewpoint for Subtraction with Borrowing

The essence of the method is as follows: for natural numbers where $a < b$, think the operation:

$$1a - b = (10 + a) - b = 10 - (b - a)$$

Here, the 10 represents the tens taken from neighbouring numbers.

We can summarize our new method as follows. Subtraction is much easier by writing the expression $10-(b-a)$, instead of $(10+a)-b$. This allows us to continuously subtract smaller numbers from larger numbers.

For example, in the operation $13 - 7$, instead of the standard way, subtract 3 from 7 to obtain 4. Then, subtract 4 from 10 to get the correct answer, 6. We believe that subtraction performed

¹ suleymanediz@yyu.edu.tr, Department of Primary Mathematics Education, Faculty of Education, Van Yüzüncü Yıl University, Türkiye

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17614595>

in this way can be taught as a new method, especially for peoples with learning disabilities, as it offers a clearer and more intuitive alternative.

However, the effectiveness of this method will only be revealed through research conducted by math teachers and mathematics educators on this topic. Since we haven't found any studies in the literature demonstrating subtraction using such this method, I thought it would be appropriate to share this idea with the world. In fact, the originator of this method is my son, Salih Selim Ediz. He used this method to subtract in elementary school. If this type subtraction hasn't been done using this method before, we believe it's appropriate to call this method "subtraction using the Ediz method."

Declarations: This study did not receive funding.